

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTIVE VIDEO LESSON IN INCREASING THE ENGLISH PROFICIENCY LEVEL AMONG GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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Effectiveness of Interactive Video Lesson in Increasing the English Proficiency Level among Grade 10 Students

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Abstract

The chapter provides an overview of the educational challenges and innovations prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the Philippines. Before the pandemic, the Philippines had a high proficiency level in education; however, recent studies show a decline in academic performance, particularly in elementary and secondary levels. The pandemic further complicated education, pushing teachers to adopt various strategies, including using interactive video lessons as supplemental learning materials. The research conducted at Manay National High School aimed to address these challenges by evaluating the effectiveness of teacher-made interactive video lessons in improving English proficiency among Grade 10 students. The study used a quasi-experimental design involving pretest and posttest assessments of two groups: the experimental group, which used interactive videos, and the control group, which did not. The results revealed that students in the experimental group showed a significant improvement in their post-test scores compared to the control group, indicating the effectiveness of the video lessons. The study concludes that interactive video lessons are a valuable tool in enhancing student learning, particularly in a self-paced, pandemic-affected educational environment. The chapter recommends the broader adoption of interactive video lessons across all subjects to help improve student proficiency and engagement during challenging times.

Keywords: *interactive video lesson, English proficiency level, grade 10 students*

Introduction

The unprecedented worldwide COVID-19 outbreak has led educational leaders to change ways how to deliver effective learning to students in various means all over the world. Educators have been utilizing different teaching strategies through various platforms to ensure that learning continues amidst the pandemic crisis.

Before the pandemic crisis, the Philippines, based on the BEI Report in 2012, attained a score above 7.0, putting the country within range of a high proficiency that indicates an ability to lead business discussions and perform complex tasks. However, various studies reveal that the quality of education in the Philippines is continuously declining. This notion is based on the results of achievement tests and board examinations. Not only are the elementary and secondary graduates affected, but passers-by of board examinations in all fields of endeavor continue to go down. One of the important causes for this phenomenon is the low academic performance in the elementary and secondary levels (Racca & Lasaten, 2016)

Despite this new normal education teachers continuously uphold the endeavor of increasing the proficiency level of the students through using various teaching strategies and supplemental learning materials. Teachers had to use other alternatives in delivering the lessons, considering the directive speech act as very important in learning interactions because it makes it easier for students to understand learning material. One of them is using digital media in the form of interactive video lessons. Interactive videos make it easier for students and teachers to deliver learning.

Video lessons are increasingly adopted in education, especially in universities and lifelong learning projects. Their popularity is due to people's familiarity with video and to other intrinsic characteristics of this medium, such as the message's rapidity and its reproducibility (Oktavia et al., 2020)

Papadopoulos and Palaigeorgiou (2016) cited Ertelt et al. (2006), stating that videos are one of the most frequently used media in classroom settings. Several studies have shown that video presents knowledge attractively and consistently, and it can improve teaching methods and increase learning outcomes. However, it is well-reported that linear video may also lead to superficial learning and unsatisfactory viability of the learning effect, a phenomenon which is called "couch-potato-attitude"

Moreover, in online courses structured by course topics, a short video is often used as part of a video lesson, as the course topic covered in the lesson does not necessarily demonstrate a how-to procedure and may require different types of instruction. Also, these video lessons often incorporate in-video quizzes or self-assessment questions to engage learners and help reinforce their learning (Berezhnaya, 2020)

Without proper facilitation, some individuals never manage to overcome the barriers that stop them from learning the lesson, especially in this new normal education setting.

The utilization of teacher-made video lessons, educators can often cover more topics and move through the content quickly. Likewise, it empowers students to take control of their own learning; they can speed up, slow down, or replay video lessons as they wish at their own pace.

Varela (2018) cited that video research may efficiently deal with methodological issues in studying the complexity of the teaching-learning processes in the classroom. Video studies can cope with inter-rated reliability problems, and they make it possible to apply multiple conceptual perspectives and involve not only researchers but also school managers, including the teachers themselves, as well as other relevant education actors.

To respond to students' differences, material content can be provided by letting students prepare themselves (e.g., studying content through online lessons, video, pre-recorded lectures, other necessary activities, etc.) in advance before the class (Jitjumong & Suksakulchai, 2019).

Lastly, videos increase student engagement, which in turn helps boost achievement. If students are interested in the material, they will process and remember it better. They offer the flexibility to pause, rewind, or skip throughout the video to have class discussions or review particular areas.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of utilizing interactive video lessons as supplemental learning materials in teaching to increase proficiency levels in English 10. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the pretest performance in terms of:
 - 1.1. control group and
 - 1.2. experimental group?
2. What is the posttest performance in terms of:
 - 2.1. control group, and
 - 2.2. experimental group?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the control and experimental group?
4. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental group?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental group?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher made use of the quasi-experimental non-equivalent design called the pretest–posttest of Campbell and Stanley (1963), as cited by Dinardo (2008).

The study is set to determine the effectiveness of utilizing interactive video as supplemental learning materials in increasing the English proficiency level. The research was carried out using a quantitative design, which involves the use of questionnaires, such as pretests and posttests. Result to elicit responses from the target audience with the view of analyzing and describing systematically.

Participants

The participants of the study are the Grade 10 level students of Manay National High School, 64 students from Section Aquarius the experimental group and 48 students from Section Aries the control group who are enrolled in Basic Education Curriculum for this school year 2021-2022. All of these participants were selected through random sampling.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Students' Performance in English of the Control Group and Experimental Group based on their Post-test Mean Scores*

Post-test		Mean	SD	Description
		Scores		
Students Performance in English	Control Group	28.81	5.26	Moderate
Students' Performance in English	Control Group	28.81	5.26	Moderate
	Experimental Group	38.94	7.51	High

Table 1 presents the statistical data on the test of the significant difference in the post-test mean scores between the control group and the experimental group. The post-test mean score of the control group yielded 28.81 with an SD of 5.26, while the experimental group garnered 38.94 with an SD of 7.51. The standard deviation results indicate that the scores of students in the experimental group are more spread than the control group.

Results from the t-test revealed a computed t-value of 8.04 with a probability level of 0.000. Since the probability level is lesser than 0.05 level of significance, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students in English between the control group and the experimental group.

According to Paavizhi et al. (2019), numerous educators and teacher training institutions consider that information resources as the best possibility for modern teaching. Students in the current trend are bound to use modern materials such as video tutorials for learning

purposes for almost anything, say changing the vehicle tires to dancing. Significantly, the millennium has contributed to 92% of the videos online. quality lectures in video formats and online courses that can be accessed inside the campus.

Table 2. *Difference of Students' Performance in English of the Control Group and Experimental Group based on their Pre-test Mean Scores*

Pretest	
Control Group	Experimental Group
26.63	27.45

Table 2 presented the significant difference of students' performance in their pretest mean scores. The control group got 26.63 while the experimental got 27.45. Data revealed that there was a moderate difference. This means that students' learning output in English is just a satisfactory.

Tullis and Benjamin (2010) cited that metacognitive monitoring and control must be accurate and efficient in order to allow self-guided learners to improve their performance. Yet few examples exist in which allowing learners to control learning produces higher levels of performance than restricting learners' control.

Table 3. *Difference of Students' Performance in English of the Control Group and Experimental Group based on Post-test Mean Scores*

Posttest	
Control Group	Experimental Group
28.81	38.94

Table 3 presents the significant difference in students' performance in their posttest mean scores. The control group got 28.81 while the experimental got 38.94. Data revealed that there was a significant difference in the performance of students in the experimental group compared to the control group. This means that students' learning output in English during the utilization of video lesson is high which implies a very satisfactory learning output.

Table 4. *Difference of Students' Performance in English of the Control Group and Experimental Group based on their Pre-Test & Post-test Mean Scores*

	Pretest	Posttest
Control	26.63	28.81
Experimental	27.45	38.94

Table 4 presented the significant difference of students' performance on the control and experimental group based in their pretest and posttest mean scores. The control group got 26.31 during pretest and 28.81 on the posttest. While the experimental got 27.45 during pretest and 38.94 on the posttest. Data revealed that there was a high significant difference in the performance of students in the experimental group compared to the control group. Therefore, it was clearly conveyed that intervention made was effective.

Ningthoujam (2016) cited Sayed (2013), video-based lectures offer more successes and reduce failures in the immediate and follow-up measures as compared with the traditional method (without video) of teaching human anatomy and physiology that was based on printout illustrations, but these differences were not statistically significant.

Conclusions

Based on the results, the utilization of teacher made video lesson as intervention in raising the proficiency level of the Grade 10- English students were found effective. In the implementation of self-paced learning, it has been proven that student learns best when they have something to view as their reference and guide in answering their modules than merely using the printed self-learning modules.

According to Sholikhah et al. (2019) interactive learning media is a learning process tool that can be used to convey learning material by combining different innovations to make it more interesting. One example of learning media is interactive video learning. One example of learning media is interactive media is interactive video learning media in the form of video media which is used as a learning tool to be made as attractive as possible so that the delivery of learning material is more easily to understood.

Moreover, Woolfit (2015) cited that video is permeating our educational institutions, transforming the way we teach, learn, study, communicate, and work. Harnessing the power of video to achieve improved outcomes—for example, a better grade in exams/assignments or more effective knowledge transfer—is becoming an essential skill. A key pillar in the drive towards improved digital literacy, video brings considerable benefits to educational institutions: streamlined admission, increased retention, and improved learning outcomes.

Lastly, video addresses cognitive design issues by combining various modal displays of content to allow richer details of the procedure

to rise to the surface. Users can attune to the spoken message, which will have different details than what is visible in the video or the accompanying text. In this way, videos help address issues like a lack of detail and level matching. Finally, videos can address affective design issues as well. For some, videos are engaging and easier to consume than a book (Obagah & Bresibe, 2017)

The following are recommended for future actions: The utilization of interactive video, especially this time during the pandemic crisis where self-paced is implemented, is highly recommended to be institutionalized. Teachers should innovate more interactive video lessons to motivate students to learn best amidst pandemic and to be able to increase their proficiency level. The utilization of interactive video lesson must use across all subjects to serve as guide and reference of the students for them to be able to increase their proficiency level.

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